

vACE: Exploring the Design Space of Vector Processing Units for Soft Error Vulnerability

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Abstract—Vector architectures have re-emerged as a key component of high-performance computing, offering scalable parallelism for data-intensive workloads. The open and extensible RISC-V instruction set architecture (ISA) further accelerates innovation in this domain, enabling flexible design and exploration of vector processing units (VPUs). In this work, we present the first implementation of an Architecturally Correct Execution (ACE) analysis framework for vector processing units (VPUs) in gem5, demonstrated on a RISC-V VPU model, enabling estimation of failure rates due to transient faults across a broad design space. Our implementation targets the largest (and thus most vulnerable) hardware structures: Vector Register File (VRF), data cache (D-Cache), and L2-Cache, analyzing ACE behavior across various configurations of these components. We conduct experiments using both scalar and vectorized versions of a benchmark suite, tested with multiple input sizes. The goal is to measure the Architectural Vulnerability Factor (AVF) of a VPU design and identify architectural components that are most susceptible to soft errors. Our results demonstrate how vectorization, workload characteristics, and hardware parameters affect ACE behavior, providing valuable insights for improving the reliability of modern VPU architectures.

Index Terms—reliability, vector processing units, transient faults, microarchitecture, architectural vulnerability factor, FIT rate, Goodput

I. INTRODUCTION

The openness and modularity of the RISC-V instruction set architecture (ISA) have attracted widespread attention in the computing industry [1]. RISC-V provides a flexible foundation suitable for a wide range of applications, including embedded systems, edge computing [2], and high-performance computing (HPC) [3]. One of RISC-V’s most notable features is its extensibility, which enables the integration of custom extensions to meet specific computational requirements [4]. A prominent example is the V (Vector) extension [5], ratified in late 2021, which enhances RISC-V’s ability to support applications that exploit data parallelism, reduce code size, increase instruction bandwidth, and improve energy efficiency.

A wide range of modern applications—including machine learning, graphics, digital signal processing, and cryptography—rely on algorithms designed to fully exploit vector instructions such as those provided by the RISC-V Vector extension. As these workloads grow in complexity and scale, particularly in high-performance and data-intensive environments, the reliability of vector processors becomes increasingly critical. Hardware faults in vector units can lead to silent data corruptions or system crashes, thereby compromising

correctness. Due to the inherently data-intensive nature of vector processing units (VPUs), most hardware faults in these units are likely to manifest as data corruptions. This is especially concerning in domains where accuracy and availability are paramount, such as scientific computing and real-time data analysis. Ensuring the fault tolerance of vector processors requires a combination of hardware-level redundancy, software-based error detection, and algorithmic resilience. As discussed in [6], fault tolerance techniques are essential for maintaining system reliability in high-performance computing, and these principles are equally important when applied to vector processing units.

To evaluate and improve processor reliability, it is essential to understand which hardware faults actually affect program behavior. To this end, the Architectural Vulnerability Factor (AVF) [7] was introduced as a metric to quantify the likelihood that a fault in a hardware structure will propagate and result in a program-visible error. The concept of AVF applies to any computing element: CPU, GPU, etc. Two prevalent methods for estimating AVF are Architecturally Correct Execution (ACE) analysis [8] and Statistical Fault Injection (SFI) [9], [10]. While SFI can provide accurate results [11], it is always significantly time-consuming and resource-intensive [12], [13]. In contrast, ACE analysis offers a more efficient alternative by analytically identifying vulnerable bits without the need for extensive simulation. Furthermore, several studies [14], [15] have shown that the inherent conservatism of ACE can be mitigated by incorporating various fault masking conditions, while still maintaining its advantage of fast and scalable AVF estimation.

In this paper, we introduce vACE, the first AVF estimation framework for vector processor designs using ACE analysis. We leverage the open-source RISC-V vector processor design from [16], integrated into the gem5 simulator [17], [18], the widely-used cycle-level simulation platform.

The main contributions of this work are:

- 1) We extend the open-source RISC-V vector processor from [16] to support ACE analysis in key hardware components, such as the Vector Register File (VRF) and the cache hierarchy.
- 2) We perform design space exploration across various vector hardware configurations.
- 3) We provide insights into the impact of different hardware configurations and input sizes on the AVF behavior of

benchmarks from the open-source suite [16], [19].

- 4) We propose vector configurations by integrating existing performance findings with vulnerability analysis results.

II. BACKGROUND

A. ACE Analysis

Architectural Correct Execution (ACE) analysis is a foundational methodology for estimating the architectural vulnerability of hardware structures to transient faults, such as soft errors. Originally proposed by Mukherjee et al. [8], ACE analysis determines whether a bit flip in a hardware structure is likely to affect the final program output. Bits whose corruption can influence the visible architectural state (e.g., register file, memory, I/O) are termed ACE bits, while others are un-ACE bits and are considered fault-masked or inconsequential.

To quantify the vulnerability of a hardware structure, the Architectural Vulnerability Factor (AVF) defined for a structure S during a workload W utilizing the ACE notion as:

$$AVF_{S,W} = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{\text{Bits}_S-1} \text{ACE Cycles}_i}{\text{Bits}_S \cdot \text{Cycles}_W} \quad (1)$$

Here, the AVF of a hardware structure is defined as the ratio of the total number of cycles during which each bit holds ACE-relevant data to the total number of bit-cycles in the structure over the execution of the workload.

As shown in Equation 1, computing the AVF of a hardware structure requires the identification of the time intervals during which each bit holds data that can affect the program output (referred to as ACE), and distinguishing them from periods where the data is inconsequential (un-ACE). By design [8], ACE analysis is a conservative methodology—assuming bits are ACE unless there is definitive evidence to classify them as un-ACE.

Sources of un-ACE bits generally fall into two categories: microarchitectural and architectural.

Microarchitectural un-ACE bits include:

- *Idle or Invalid State*: Bits that are inactive or hold invalid data.
- *Mis-speculated State*: Bits associated with incorrect speculative execution, such as squashed instructions.
- *Performance Structures*: Bits in speculative structures like branch predictors, which do not influence committed program state.
- *Ex-ACE State*: Bits that were once ACE but become un-ACE after their last architectural use—such as dead register values or state not visible to the architecture.

In addition, Wang et al. [11] introduced the notion of *Y-bits*—dynamic instances of bits that, while capable of dramatically altering the course of execution in the processor, do not ultimately affect architecturally correct execution. As a result, their values are considered un-ACE. However, Y-bits cannot be defined using a single run, and may require fault injection experiments to be accurately identified, which increases the conservatism of ACE analysis. Biswas et al. [14] later argued

that the impact of Y-bits is less significant than the inherent conservatism of ACE analysis as a whole.

Architectural un-ACE bits include:

- *NOP Instructions*: All fields other than the opcode are un-ACE, as they have no effect on program behavior.
- *Performance-Enhancing Instructions*: For example, faults in non-opcode fields of prefetch instructions typically do not affect program correctness.
- *Dynamically Dead (DD) Instructions*: These are instructions whose results are never used, and thus their output bits are un-ACE. Detection of DD instructions is usually limited to a finite instruction window.
- *Logical Masking*: Some operand bits, while part of a computational chain, do not affect the final outcome.

Fig. 1: Example operations of various hardware bits over time

Figure 1 depicts some examples of ACE and un-ACE intervals of different hardware bits over time. Red intervals denote ACE periods (a flipped bit in them matters), while green intervals indicate un-ACE periods (a flipped bit in them does not matter). Despite the different actions shown, the two bits in Figures 1a and 1b have the same ACE cycles. A general observation is that intervals ending with a read action are considered ACE, whereas those ending with a write action are un-ACE. In Figure 1b, various memory operations are shown. As discussed in [20], the fill-to-evict interval is un-ACE, while in a write-back cache, the write-to-evict interval is considered ACE for a dirty block. Additionally, the evict-to-fill interval is un-ACE due to the invalid state, and the fill-to-read interval is ACE.

As previously discussed, each ACE interval can be shortened due to masking effects from the architectural state. However, accurately determining how a bit will be used—and whether it will influence the program output—is often impractical, particularly in complex systems and workloads. This challenge is further compounded by ISA-dependent behavior. As a result, ACE analysis is known to exhibit significant inaccuracy, often overestimating the vulnerability of hardware structures [11], [21], [22].

Despite this limitation (which yet remains to be analyzed on different hardware units, workloads, and ISAs), ACE analysis provides a major advantage: it estimates vulnerability using just one fault-free simulation by inferring the outcome had

faults not occurred. This allows it to approximate the cumulative effects of thousands of fault injections in a single simulation pass, resulting in AVF computation speeds that are orders of magnitude faster—often 1000x—compared to traditional statistical fault injection (SFI).

B. The *gem5* simulator

gem5 [17], [18] is the leading open-source simulator for computer architecture research and microarchitecture design space exploration. Widely used for reliability studies [13], [23]–[28], typically via software-based fault injection (SFI), this work presents the first complete ACE-based analysis implementation in *gem5*. The simulator’s modular framework supports a broad range of processor models, from simple in-order cores to complex out-of-order designs, and offers both syscall emulation (SE) and full-system (FS) simulation modes. With support for multiple ISAs—including x86, ARM, SPARC, and RISC-V—*gem5* enables cross-architecture comparison and experimentation. Ongoing community contributions have made *gem5* a robust, flexible, and widely adopted tool for performance evaluation and architectural research in both academia and industry.

1) *gem5* & RISC-V support: *gem5* offers robust support for the RISC-V ISA, with both SE and FS simulation. Since RISC-V FS support was merged in 2021, *gem5* allows researchers to boot Linux, run suites like BusyBox and PARSEC, and model privileged instructions, interrupts, and virtual memory in detail [29]. This enables realistic studies of OS behavior, virtualization, device drivers, and full applications at cycle-level accuracy.

For full-system experiments, *gem5* provides prebuilt, calibrated RISC-V board models that closely mirror real hardware. Validated by Pathak et al. [30], these models yield simulation errors of only 19–23% on SPEC CPU2017, enhancing accuracy and reproducibility.

With access to validated, high-fidelity RISC-V full-system models, researchers are well-positioned not only to evaluate existing systems but also to explore novel architectural enhancements. One of *gem5*’s defining strengths lies in its modular and extensible architecture, which allows for the integration of custom instructions, specialized memory systems, and new execution units. This flexibility makes *gem5* especially valuable for prototyping and analyzing emerging RISC-V extensions targeting domain-specific acceleration, energy-efficient computing, and memory-intensive workloads. Ongoing efforts include the implementation of the RISC-V Hypervisor (H) extension [31], which introduces support for hardware-assisted virtualization—an important feature for cloud and security-focused architectures. Furthermore, support for the RISC-V Vector (V) extension was officially merged into *gem5* version 23.1 [32], enabling vectorized computation in both SE and FS modes with user-configurable vector parameters.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodology employed in this work, which builds upon an existing decoupled RISC-V Vector

Processing Unit (VPU) integrated into the *gem5* simulator. The primary contribution of our work is the implementation of ACE analysis within the vector datapath, for the first time. Specifically, ACE analysis was incorporated into the VRF and the cache hierarchy to enable precise evaluation of reliability-related behavior for the most vulnerable hardware units of the VPU. The final part of this section describes the benchmark suite used to evaluate the VPU, along with the approach taken to isolate statistical metrics within the region of interest for each benchmark.

A. A Vector Architecture model in *gem5*

The RISC-V VPU implemented in [16] represents the first open-source, decoupled vector architecture integrated into the *gem5* simulator. It fully supports version 0.7 of the RISC-V Vector extension (RVV v0.7), significantly extending *gem5*’s capabilities. This implementation introduces support for a wide range of vector lengths and is fully parameterizable, enabling researchers to explore diverse architectural configurations tailored to specific experimental goals. We harness these capabilities of the VPU design for our ACE-based reliability exploration of such designs.

The VPU follows a decoupled architecture that separates scalar and vector execution into distinct units, allowing for concurrent operation. The scalar core (Minor CPU in *gem5*) is responsible for fetching and decoding vector instructions, which are treated as no-operations (NOPs) within the scalar pipeline. Once these instructions reach the commit stage, they are forwarded to the VPU by the *VectorEngineInterface* for execution. This design ensures minimal interference with scalar control flow while maintaining synchronization between scalar and vector domains.

Upon arrival at the VPU, vector instructions undergo register renaming to eliminate false dependencies and maximize instruction-level parallelism. The VPU features separate arithmetic and memory issue queues, allowing memory and computational operations to be issued independently. Instructions are held in these queues until their operands are ready and the relevant execution units are available.

A key component of the architecture is its configurable multi-lane structure. Each lane handles a subset of the VRF, which is partitioned across lanes. This setup allows for scalable parallelism while preserving locality. Inter-lane communication, necessary for operations such as slides, reductions, and gathers, is supported by configurable interconnects—including ring and crossbar topologies—chosen based on performance and area trade-offs.

Memory access is managed by the Vector Memory Unit (VMU), which supports unit-stride, strided, and indexed (gather/scatter) addressing modes. The VMU generates memory requests and interleaves them across lanes. Data fetched from memory is distributed through dedicated channels to their corresponding lanes, while store operations are managed using buffered writes. This ensures efficient data movement and aligns with the vector memory access patterns.

Parameter	Value
Scalar Core	Dual-issue 64-bit RISC-V in-order pipeline @ 2.0 GHz
Vector Engine	Vector Processing Unit @ 1.0 GHz
Active lanes	1, 2, 4, 8
Max Vector Length (MVL)	512 bit (8×64 bit), 1024 bit (16×64 bit), 2048 bit (32×64 bit), 4096 bit (64×64 bit), 8192 bit (128×64 bit)
Vector Physical Registers	40
Vector Register File	Max Vector Length x Vector Physical Registers
Vector Arithmetic Units	1 pipelined ALU per Lane
Vector Memory Unit	Single memory port to L2 (512-bit bus)
I-Cache	32 KB, 4-way, 512-bit block size, 4-cycle latency
D-Cache	32 KB, 4-way, 512-bit block size, 4-cycle latency
L2-Cache	256 KB, 8-way, 512-bit block size, 12-cycle latency
Main Memory	2 GB DDR3 DRAM

TABLE I: Summary of the microarchitectural configuration parameters and their supported values.

To maintain execution consistency, the design includes a Reorder Buffer (ROB) that enforces in-order instruction commit, as well as a Valid-Bit structure to track operand readiness. Together, these elements support out-of-order execution within the VPU while preserving program order and correctness.

Despite some limitations due to its development time—specifically, the lack of FS mode support for RISC-V in gem5 and the provisional status of the RVV specification at the time—the VPU remains a valuable and robust research platform. Notably, features such as atomic and permutation operations were not yet implemented, and exception handling is constrained by the use of SE mode. Nevertheless, the architecture’s open-source nature, modularity, and transparency make it particularly well-suited for academic exploration. It enables detailed evaluation of vector execution in isolation from scalar execution, a property that is especially beneficial for studying the impact of vectorization on different fields, e.g performance and vulnerability. The design has also been validated through a comprehensive benchmark suite, ensuring its utility and reproducibility in research contexts.

B. ACE implementation

This section describes the modifications made to the vector model presented in Section III-A to enable ACE lifetime analysis. In addition, new statistics have been introduced into gem5, including occupancy metrics and cycle distributions across different lifetime intervals, such as read-to-read intervals and others, for the detailed elaboration on our VPU vulnerability findings.

1) *Vector Register File*: In the vector model described in [16], the VRF is managed by the *VectorRegister*, which interfaces with the *VectorEngine* through ports responsible for handling read and write requests. These requests are generated once an instruction is issued from the *Vector Instruction Queue*, and are serviced by transferring data either from the

VRF to the request packet during a read operation, or from the request packet to the VRF during a write operation.

ACE analysis monitors every operation that affects each byte of the VRF and determines the ACE cycles by identifying both write-to-read and read-to-read intervals. Specifically, for each accessed byte, the analysis accumulates the number of cycles between a write and the subsequent read, or between two consecutive reads, representing the periods during which the data remains vulnerable. Since all vector instructions in the VPU are always committed by the scalar core, this approach ensures accurate detection of micro-architecturally un-ACE bits and enables reliable estimation of the AVF.

2) *Caches*: The gem5 simulator supports write-back caches that communicate with the CPU and memory buses through dedicated ports. For each memory request, the cache checks its tag array to determine whether the access results in a hit or a miss. In the case of a hit, several actions may be performed depending on the type of request: a write-back may occur if the request originates from another cache; a read operation may involve copying a portion of the matched cache block into the request packet; or a write operation may overwrite the corresponding block with the packet’s data, marking it as dirty.

The *Vector Memory Unit* (VMU) is connected to the L2-Cache, as indicated in Table I. When a load instruction is issued from the *Vector Instruction Queue*, a virtual-to-physical address translation is initiated. Once this translation completes, the VMU generates a request for an entire cache block from the L2-Cache. If the data is not found (i.e., on a cache miss), additional requests may be triggered, such as to main memory. After the data is retrieved, it is partitioned across the vector lanes, with each lane receiving its corresponding portion and writing it back to the Vector Register File. A similar but reverse process is followed for store instructions: each lane reads a fixed amount of data from the VRF, determined by the configurable VRF line size, expressed in bytes per lane. Once the read completes, the data is issued as a write request to the cache. This tightly coordinated memory access mechanism enables efficient vector data movement between memory and computation units.

In [20], the concept of ACE lifetime for data arrays is formally defined. In this work, we implement ACE lifetime analysis for both the D-Cache and L2-Cache. Our framework monitors every cache block access and records ACE intervals based on the analytical model presented in [20], incorporating byte-level sensitivity to enhance the accuracy of the vulnerability analysis.

A key aspect of ACE analysis is how speculative execution impacts cache accesses. In our framework, using the gem5 Minor CPU core (see Section III-A), speculative memory instructions are only executed if they will commit, preventing speculative pollution in the D-Cache and L2-Cache from memory instructions. However, instruction cache accesses differ: instruction fetches occur early, before branch outcomes are known, so many speculatively fetched instruction blocks may never be used. Mutlu et al. [33] found that about 30% of I-

Cache blocks fetched during SPEC2000 benchmarks are never used, though this effect is much less at L2. Importantly, we do not subtract all unused speculative instruction blocks from ACE AVF, as most only fill the cache and each block may contain critical bits. Thus, for a conservative and robust assessment, we classify all cache accesses requesting instructions as ACE.

C. The RiVEC Benchmark Suite

The RiVEC Benchmark Suite, developed by Ramírez et al. [16], [19], is a collection of data-parallel applications spanning various computational domains. It provides both scalar (serial) and vectorized implementations targeting the RISC-V ISA. The vectorized versions are written using RISC-V Vector C intrinsics and are designed to cover a wide portion of the RISC-V Vector Extension functionality. Originally aligned with version 0.7 of the RISC-V Vector extension, the benchmark suite has been updated to support the ratified RVV v1.0 specification. In addition, it includes scripts to facilitate execution on multiple simulation and emulation platforms, including Spike [34], gem5 [17], [18], and QEMU [35].

In this work, we use the branch of the RiVEC suite targeting RVV v0.7 to maintain consistency with the vector model. To enable fine-grained vulnerability analysis, we modify the benchmark source files by inserting gem5’s *m5* pseudoinstructions to mark the Region of Interest (ROI) within each application. This approach allows us to focus on the core computational kernel of each benchmark, ensuring that only the most reliability-critical and vector-intensive phases are considered during statistics collection. An example of this instrumentation is shown in Listing 1. All benchmarks are compiled using the LLVM-EPI-0.7 toolchain, which supports RVV v0.7 intrinsics and ensures full compatibility with the vector model used in our simulation framework.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we present AVF results for the VRF and data caches across a total of 20 different vector configurations (Table I), using the ten workloads from the suite

```

1 #include <stdio.h>
2 #include <stdlib.h>
3 #include "m5op.h"
4
5 ...
6
7 int main (int argc, char **argv)
8 {
9     ...
10    /* initialization part */
11    ...
12    /* kernel (ROI) part start */
13    m5_reset_stats(0, 0);
14    ...
15    /* kernel (ROI) part finish */
16    m5_dump_stats(0, 0);
17    /* output part */
18    ...
19    return 0;
20 }

```

Listing 1: Modified benchmark code to collect statistics within the ROI.

described in Section III-C, with various input sizes (i.e. tiny, small, medium, and large). We also provide configuration recommendations based on AVF observations. All experiments were performed on an AMD EPYC 7402 24-Core CPU (96 hyperthreads) with 128GB of DDR4 RAM.

Figure 2 presents simulation time for scalar and vector executions across the ten benchmarks using the small, medium, and large input sizes of the benchmarks. The bar plots correspond to scalar simulation times, which are consistent for each workload-input pair, as they are measured under a single, fixed configuration. In contrast, overlaid markers depict the minimum, average, and maximum simulation times for vector executions, derived from 20 different vector configurations combining various MVL widths and lane counts, as detailed in Table I. Notably, for the majority of benchmarks, the average vector simulation time is lower than the scalar counterpart. This reduction is particularly evident in benchmarks such as *lavaMD* and *somier*, where the minimum vector time is significantly shorter. Conversely, in benchmarks like *cannear* and *particlefilter*, the scalar execution time remains lower than both the average and maximum vector times, highlighting the simulation overhead introduced by the vector model.

Another notable insight from Figure 2 is its implicit demonstration of the advantage offered by ACE analysis. With just a single simulation run, ACE enables the calculation of AVF values for all relevant components, incurring only a modest overhead (less than 10%, not shown in the figure). In contrast, traditional fault injection (SFI) techniques would require an impractical amount of time to analyze all vector configurations. For example, estimating the AVF of the *lavaMD* benchmark with the large input size with 1000 injections (5% error margin with 99.8% confidence level [10]) on a hardware structure and an average simulation time of 87000 seconds each, would take more than two years to complete:

$$87000 \frac{\text{seconds}}{\text{execution}} \times 1000 \text{ executions} \approx 2.75 \text{ years}$$

Fig. 2: Simulation time for each benchmark under scalar and vectorized configurations.

Therefore, for long-running workloads, measuring AVF through fast ACE analysis is the only practical way to explore

the broad design space of VPU microarchitecture—as is the case for CPUs and GPUs.

A. Vulnerability Analysis of VRF

Figure 3 illustrates the AVF values derived through ACE alongside the VRF utilization across the evaluated workloads within the ROI, using medium input sizes. Each graph corresponds to a fixed MVL configuration—1024, 2048, and 4096 bits, respectively. Within each graph, the AVF values are shown for varying lane widths (from 1 to 8 lanes). The bar charts represent AVF percentages, while the overlaid line plots indicate VRF utilization.

Figure 4 presents a complementary view, this time fixing the number of lanes—2, 4, and 8— and varying the MVL width. Each subplot captures the AVF and VRF behavior as MVL increases from 512 to 8192 bits.

Observation #1: The AVF varies directly with lane count and inversely with MVL: at a fixed MVL, adding more lanes increases AVF by concentrating register-file demand, while at a fixed lane count, enlarging the MVL reduces AVF by spreading data over a larger register file.

Across all these six graphs, the right y-axis indicates the percentage of VRF utilization, defined as the ratio of utilized VRF bytes to the total VRF size, while the left y-axis displays the AVF. Notably, VRF utilization is consistently higher than the corresponding AVF. This relationship follows directly from the definition of ACE, where utilization acts as an upper bound for vulnerability. Specifically, if a VRF byte is never accessed during execution, it is un-ACE. If it is accessed intermittently, it may be ACE at some points and un-ACE at others; however, utilization metrics count any access as "used", regardless of its ACE status.

In addition, AVF tends to decrease as the MVL increases. Increasing the MVL enlarges the total number of bits in the VRF, thereby diluting the impact of accesses across a larger storage space—without necessarily increasing the number of bytes accessed. Conversely, AVF increases with the number of lanes. This is due to the fact that, in the vector architecture model, the VRF is shared across all lanes.

As explained in [16], each lane interacts with an independent subset of the overall VRF. Therefore, increasing the number of lanes results in more subsets being accessed, ultimately increasing the number of VRF bytes that are vulnerable.

The utilization curves of the VRF exhibit a consistent pattern across all vector model configurations. This indicates that the relative utilization trends among benchmarks are determined primarily by the workload characteristics, rather than by changes in MVL or lane count. For instance, *lavaMD* and *blackscholes* consistently achieve the highest VRF utilization across all configurations, reflecting their register file activity. In contrast, *axpy* and *streamcluster* consistently show the lowest utilization, indicating limited register file activity.

A similar pattern is observed with AVF. Figure 5 presents AVF and VRF utilization across the evaluated workloads using

Fig. 3: AVF and Utilized Bytes of VRF per Benchmark for different values of MVL

different input sizes under three representative configurations selected at random. These results are similar with those from all other configurations examined—across five MVL values and four lane counts—indicating that the relative AVF behavior is stable regardless of the specific vector configuration. Consequently, the AVF ranking among these workloads is determined primarily by their inherent characteristics and remains largely unaffected by the underlying architectural configuration.

We now examine the impact of benchmark input size on both AVF and VRF utilization. As shown in Figure 5, VRF utilization appears largely unaffected by input size, suggest-

(a) Lanes = 2

(b) Lanes = 4

(c) Lanes = 8

Fig. 4: AVF and Utilized Bytes of VRF per Benchmark for different values of lanes

ing no strong correlation between the two. A minor exception is observed in the *Jacobi-2d* benchmark. In Figures 5a and 5b, the utilization increases slightly—by approximately $\% \Delta \text{Utilized} \approx 6\%$ —when moving from the tiny to the small input size. In Figure 5c, a different pattern emerges: the tiny and small inputs exhibit similar utilization, while the medium and large inputs show a higher level.

(a) Configuration of MVL = 512 bits & Lanes = 1

(b) Configuration of MVL = 1024 bits & Lanes = 4

(c) Configuration of MVL = 4096 bits & Lanes = 2

Fig. 5: AVF and Utilized Bytes of VRF per Benchmark for different input sizes

Observation #2: The VRF-byte utilization curves maintain their overall shape and benchmark ranking as either lanes or MVL increases, despite changes in absolute values. However, each benchmark affects how much utilization deviates from the true AVF, highlighting the necessity of ACE analysis for reliable vulnerability assessment.

In contrast, AVF varies more noticeably with input size. While most benchmarks show only minor changes, *lavaMD* exhibits a marked increase in AVF as input size grows. As

Fig. 6: Cache AVF heatmaps: whole program (a, c), ROI only (b, d).

seen in Figure 5b, the AVF for large inputs is nearly four times higher than for tiny inputs—a rise of about 300%. This shift is due to changes in instruction mix: for small inputs, *lavaMD* executes mostly scalar instructions, but as the input size grows, the proportion and number of vector instructions rise sharply, reaching about 70% of the dynamic instruction count for the largest inputs. This increased vector instruction activity leads to higher vulnerability in the vector register file.

Observation #3: Based on these benchmark results, the relative ordering of AVF across benchmarks remains consistent and is unaffected by changes in the vector configuration. Although modifying the number of lanes or the vector length can significantly affect the absolute AVF values, it does not alter the ranking of the benchmarks according to their AVF.

B. Vulnerability Analysis of Caches

Figure 6 presents heatmaps of rank-based vulnerability scores for the D-Cache and L2-Cache across the vector configurations in Table I, using all benchmarks with medium input sizes from Section III-C. Unlike the VRF, where AVF trends are more predictable with respect to MVL and lane count, cache vulnerabilities do not exhibit clear monotonic relationships across configurations. Therefore, heatmaps are used instead of traditional plots to more effectively capture and compare the overall vulnerability landscape across all vector configurations. Each heatmap compares results for the full execution (Figures 6a and 6c) and within the ROI (Figures 6b and 6d). The x-axis denotes the MVL, the y-axis shows the number of vector lanes, and the color intensity reflects the aggregated rank percentage, with darker cells indicating higher vulnerability. These ranks are computed by aggregating the relative AVF positions of each configuration across all benchmarks, effectively grading each configuration’s vulnerability in comparison to the others. This ranking approach allows the gradients to illustrate how MVL and lane count impact cache vulnerability.

Observation #4: In most cases, input size has minimal impact on VRF utilization and only slight impact on the AVF.

It is evident that cache vulnerability rankings can differ substantially depending on whether the analysis is performed over the entire benchmark execution or restricted to the ROI. In particular, Figure 6a reveals that the D-Cache vulnerability rankings tend to increase with larger MVL values and higher lane counts, indicating a growing sensitivity under more aggressive vector configurations. Conversely, the ROI-focused heatmaps for both caches (Figures 6b and 6d) show more balanced and uniformly distributed rankings, suggesting that the pronounced vulnerability seen in full-run measurements may be dominated by activity outside the ROI. Additionally, Figure 6c exhibits a distinct pyramid-like pattern, with peak vulnerability occurring at mid-range MVL values combined with the highest lane counts, highlighting a notable difference in the ranking distribution compared to the D-Cache.

Observation #5: The ranking of vector configurations by Cache AVF across benchmarks can vary depending on whether AVF is measured over the full execution or only within the ROI.

Another noteworthy observation is that, for both the D-Cache and L2-Cache, increasing the number of vector lanes generally raises the configuration’s rank relative to others. However, the maximum vector length (MVL) consistently peaks at 2048, independent of lane count. It is important to note that Figure 6 can be misleading; a configuration’s rank might improve either because its own AVF rises or because AVFs of other configurations within the same benchmark decline. Thus, analyzing AVF curves for each benchmark individually is necessary for clarity.

Figure 7 presents heatmaps of the L2-Cache AVF for all benchmarks and configurations, focusing on the L2-Cache due to its direct role in VMU memory requests. Most heatmaps appear nearly monochromatic, with AVF varying mainly by benchmark rather than configuration. Changing vector configurations generally has little effect on AVF, except for the *swaptions* benchmark, where AVF peaks sharply at MVL 4096—a pattern seen both over the full run and within the ROI. Increasing vector lanes primarily improves performance by parallelizing work, but does not affect the instruction mix or total memory requests, leading to only minor changes in access timing. In contrast, varying MVL has a more noticeable impact: while AVF differences are typically small, *swaptions*

Fig. 7: L2-Cache AVF heatmap per benchmark

shows significant variation. Larger MVL values improve performance through greater data parallelism and can require more cache blocks to fill registers (e.g., a vlw instruction with VL exceeding the cache block size), thus potentially shifting cache access patterns and influencing AVF outcomes.

We now examine the impact of vectorization on L2-Cache AVF compared to its scalar counterpart. Figure 8 contrasts the scalar AVF with the minimum and maximum AVFs observed under vectorized configurations, focusing only on the region of interest (ROI) within benchmarks using the medium input size. The figure also includes cache utilization percentages, which—as previously demonstrated with the VRF—serve as an upper bound for the AVF. In the vast majority of cases, the scalar AVF is lower than even the minimum AVF recorded in the vectorized environment, highlighting the importance of the direct connection between the VMU and the L2-Cache.

Observation #6: Neither lane count, nor the MVL significantly affects the AVF of the L2-Cache. The dominant factor is the benchmark code.

Despite the generally consistent trends, two observations from Figure 8 require further discussion. First, *lavaMD* exhibits a significant AVF difference—about 192%—between its scalar and vectorized versions, likely due to a substantial (45%) difference in L2-Cache miss rate. Fewer cache misses in the scalar version mean more ACE intervals occur, as cache hits—especially on reads—can generate ACE intervals. Second, in only one benchmark (*swaptions*), the AVF of the scalar configuration surpass the lowest vectorized AVF (MVL = 512, lanes = 8). In all other benchmarks, every vectorized configuration yields an L2-Cache AVF higher than the scalar baseline. This exception is linked to increased D-Cache accesses and reduced L2-Cache utilization, as the configuration’s small MVL and high D-Cache activity lead to minimal L2-Cache requests. Overall, as also shown in Figure 7, any change affecting cache access timing can influence the AVF calculation through its effect on ACE intervals.

Observation #7: Vectorizing memory operations increases the L2-Cache AVF compared to the scalar version.

C. Design Suggestions

Ramírez et al. [16] present a detailed vector architecture model in *gem5*, evaluating performance gains of vectorized benchmarks across varying MVL and lane configurations. Their results show that speedup depends largely on the data-level parallelism (DLP) of each benchmark, with greater DLP enabling larger speedups on wider vector units. They also briefly note the impact of increasing vector hardware on silicon area.

Building on these findings, we incorporate reliability into our design considerations by utilizing *Goodput* as a metric. Although *Goodput* is originally a networking term [36], it can be adapted for the combined analysis of performance and reliability because it describes the correct execution over time.

$$\text{Goodput} = \text{Throughput} - \text{FIT} = \frac{\text{Executions}}{10^9 \text{ hours}} - \sum_S \text{FIT}_S \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FIT}_S &= \text{AVF}_S \cdot \text{raw FIT}_{\text{bit}} \cdot \text{Bits}_S \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{t_{\text{total}}} \cdot \sum_W t_W \cdot \text{AVF}_{S,W} \right) \cdot \text{raw FIT}_{\text{bit}} \cdot \text{Bits}_S \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

Equation 2 defines *Goodput* as the expected number of correct executions over 10^9 hours of operation. In this analysis, we assume a set of workloads W are executed in a round-robin fashion. *Goodput* is calculated as the total number of executions (*Throughput*) over 10^9 hours minus the number

Fig. 8: L2-Cache AVF within ROI

Fig. 9: Configuration Goodput with execution time

of failed executions, as given by the total FIT rate during the same period. The total FIT rate is computed as the sum of the FIT contributions from each individual hardware structure S , as expressed in Equation 3. The FIT rate of each structure S is determined by three main factors: (1) the weighted AVF, averaged over workloads and weighted by each workload’s execution time; (2) the raw FIT rate, which is dictated by fabrication technology and operational conditions and quantifies the fault probability per bit (for all results shown, we assume a value of 10^{-6}); and (3) the total number of bits within the structure.

Figure 9 illustrates the trade-off between average execution time and the Goodput metric for various SoC configurations, where each point is labeled by its (MVL, lanes) and colored according to its total FIT rate. The results indicate that configurations with higher MVL and more lanes—such as (4096, 8)—achieve the highest Goodput values, combining rapid execution with strong reliability. Although higher-performing configurations may exhibit slightly elevated FIT rates, the increase in throughput more than compensates for this effect, resulting in a greater number of correct executions over time. Based on these observations, the (4096, 8) configuration emerges as the most effective choice, offering the best balance of performance and reliability for applications where maximizing correct execution throughput is critical.

V. RELATED WORK

The theoretical method of ACE analysis, including the definition of the AVF, was introduced by Mukherjee et al. in [8]. Several subsequent works have extended this definition to suite in different structures. For instance, Biswas et al. [20] applied ACE analysis specifically to SRAM and CAM arrays. However, numerous studies employing practical fault injection methodologies (such as Statistical Fault Injection, SFI) have highlighted notable inaccuracies in ACE-based vulnerability estimations for various hardware components of CPUs [11], [15], [21], [22] and GPUs [37]. These inaccuracies primarily stem from oversimplified modeling. Biswas et al. [14] argue that identifying more architectural un-ACE bits can significantly reduce this inaccuracy. Nonetheless, the efficiency and relative simplicity of ACE-based AVF estimation have inspired

further research, including the creation of specialized benchmarks for component stress testing [38], the development of analysis tools such as Sim-SODA [39], the proposal of novel vulnerability metrics like multi-bit AVF [40], and methodologies aimed at reducing the overhead of fault injection experiments [41], [42].

Understanding the vulnerability of VPUs to soft errors has become a research priority. Recent studies, such as Barbirotta et al. [43] and Imianosky et al. [44], which employ RTL-based fault injection, highlight the inherent robustness and resilience strategies of RISC-V vector processing cores against transient faults.

VI. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we introduced vACE, the first vulnerability estimator specifically designed for vector processors utilizing ACE analysis. We extended a validated, decoupled open-source RISC-V vector architecture model within gem5, incorporating ACE analysis capabilities for essential hardware components, notably the VRF and data caches (D-Cache and L2-Cache). Through extensive vulnerability experiments, we calculated the AVF for these components using various vectorized benchmarks and multiple configuration scenarios.

Our analysis revealed that the AVF of the VRF correlates directly with the number of lanes, as expected due to its unified design, and is inversely proportional to MVL, primarily because of reduced initialization overhead. Conversely, we observed minimal impact of vector configuration changes on the AVF of L2-Cache. Finally, by evaluating Goodput, we have determined each configuration’s balance between performance and reliability, enabling the identification of optimal design choices that align with specific application requirements.

Looking ahead, future work will focus on integrating gem5-ACE analysis into more advanced vector models, such as a RISC-V platform with an Out-of-Order (OoO) core, full vector extension support, and system-mode capabilities for enhanced vulnerability evaluation. We also plan to refine the ACE methodology by precisely excluding un-ACE bits and expanding coverage to critical components like Instruction Queues and the Reorder Buffer, enabling a more comprehensive processor vulnerability assessment.

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